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Mathematical Competencies for Engineers

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INTRODUCTION

Mathematics as generally accepted subject forming background of engineering sciences throughout all disciplines is often questioned with respect to its real role in the engineering study programmes at technical universities worldwide. Many studies presented at SEFI conferences pointed to considerable decline in actual knowledge and understanding of mathematical concepts for engineering students nowadays. SEFI Working Group for Mathematics in Engineering Education, webpage [1], is actively dealing with this problem. Efforts of WG members resulted in introduction of new concepts, mathematical competencies, regarded necessary for future engineers to their successful professional careers. These ideas should be mirrored in new curricula design of mathematical courses for engineering students. Latest third curricula publication by SEFI MWG, see [2], that is available at the WG webpage, provides rough guidelines for design of a reasonable applied mathematics course reflecting real needs of future engineers. They urgently need to obtain several specific mathematical competencies during their studies, which could be used later in their professional scientific work in particular technical discipline, where the need to solve various applied mathematical problems appears quite often and it is necessary for successful fulfilment of the various engineering tasks themselves.

1 GENERAL CONCEPTS

1.1 Concept of mathematical competence

Concept of competence in terms of education has been recently described in various resources. Education and obtaining knowledge are activities connected to process of acquiring specific competencies during the teaching/learning process, specifically related to particular subjects. Definition of mathematical competence appeared in [3], "Mathematical competence means the ability to understand, judge, do, and use mathematics in a variety of intra and extra-mathematical contexts and situations where mathematics plays or could play a role. Necessary, but certainly not sufficient, mathematical competence prerequisites are: a lots of factual knowledge and technical skills, in the same way as vocabulary, orthography, and grammar are necessary but not sufficient prerequisites for literacy".

There exist many reasons for which the presented concept of mathematical competence was adopted for the third edition of the MWG curriculum document. One of them is the fact that the primary goal of mathematics in engineering education can be emphasized straightforwardly if we are focused on the above defined concept of mathematical competence in teaching engineering students. The ability to apply mathematical concepts and procedures in relevant contexts, and to work with engineering models and solve engineering problems using acquired mathematical knowledge and skills is essential in engineering research. Any competence requires a steady base of knowledge and skills, which is an evident idea strongly supported by many experienced teachers of mathematics at technical colleges and universities throughout the Europe. Current trends in general engineering education also support the concept of competence, which has been frequently used to describe educational goals favouring action-based knowledge over formal knowledge held just for the good performance and effectiveness at exams.

1.2 Mathematical competencies and their meaning

Eight recognised mathematical competencies, as defined in [3], can be roughly distributed into two groups, depending on their character and meaning.

The first group consists of competencies related to understanding mathematical concepts, dependencies, structures and their relations, ability to understand and apply known mathematical statements and to express own ideas mathematically in different ways. These competencies are: thinking mathematically, reasoning mathematically, representing mathematical entities, communicating in, with and about mathematics.

The other group can be recognised as a bunch of more practically oriented competencies, the ability to identify and specify mathematical problems in the practical engineering applications, to solve these problems using adequate algorithms and mathematical procedures by means of available aids and tools. Here one can include competencies: handling mathematical symbols and formalism, posing and solving mathematical problems, modelling mathematically, making use of aids and tools.

Various ideas and good practice examples of innovative competence based curricula structure applied in engineering maths courses have been presented and discussed, based on practical experience, results and deductions of numerous discussions and analyses that were presented orally or as poster contributions of participants at the SEFI MWG seminars held regularly, and addressing intentionally topics covered in this presented third edition of curriculum document. Full paper versions were printed in several issues of the Proceedings available on-line at the MWG webpage.

Many questions are arising in this context: What is the real role of mathematics in engineering education? Which mathematical competencies are most important for engineering sciences? How can we assess mathematical understanding properly?

Bi-annual seminars organized by the SEFI Working Group for Mathematics in Engineering Education at the volunteering universities throughout the Europe strive to find answers to formulated questions. Good experience and practise with various innovative scenarios of mathematics lessons and methodology of didactics are always presented by conference participants, who are real practitioners, mathematics teachers and educators at technical universities and colleges. Several European projects were initiated within the SEFI MWG members' cooperation, for instance the following three Erasmus+ Projects within the Strategic partnership call.

2 NEW INITIATIVES AND GOOD PRACTISE IDEAS

2.1 Project DrIVE-MATHS

Good experience and practise with various innovative scenarios of engineering mathematics courses appered recently in the ERAZMUS + project frame Strategic partnership. DrIVE-MATHS, Development of Innovative Mathematical Teaching Strategies in European Engineering Degrees, is project aimed at developing a novel and integrated framework to teach math classes in engineering courses at the university level. Maths department at the Politechnical Institute in Porto, Portugal is the project coordinator, and partners are from University of Claude Bernard 1, Lyon, France, Technical University in Chemnitz, Germany, and Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, see webpage [4].

The traditional way of teaching math classes based on a 'teaching by telling', or 'chalk and talk' approach, especially in the first years of the university degrees, proved to be no more acceptable. It is characterized by large classes and single-discipline teaching, based on lecture-based delivery. Recently there has been a growing interest, by the engineering professionals and the bodies for accrediting engineering degrees, in promoting a change in this paradigm. The proposed new teaching paradigm consists in the implementation of slight adaptation of course curricula, more emphasize on the problem-based-learning (PBL) approach, and learning by doing (hands-on). Application of the EduScrum as a pedagogical approach, promoting active learning (AL) by working in real world engineering problems and Jigsaw - as opposite to teacher centred methods will be introduced for basic mathematics courses in bachelor programmes.

In the PBL curriculum, students achieve competences, analyze, identify and solve problems, by relating disciplines to each other. Students develop competences such as critical thinking, agility and adaptability, communication, collaboration, initiative, analyzing and conceptualizing information, curiosity and imagination. They are an active part of their learning process and the teacher acts as a guide by proposing new research directions, methods, and tools. Hands-on experimentation, or learning-by-doing, is an essential part of the knowledge process. It enhances the desire to learn, promotes self-learning skills, and offers an efficient involvement of math subjects and engineering environments.

EduScrum creates an environment where students are the owners of their knowledge, increasing the sense of self-initiative and entrepreneurship. Applying the EduScrum methodology enhances collaborative learning, emphasizing the students' interactions with each other. Students are involved in small groups and work towards a common goal – learning, while being evaluated individually. In this sense, the math curricula teaching will be modernized and updated to include these new methodological teaching strategies. This modernization may contribute to award the EUR-ACE (European Accreditation of European Programs) to accredited engineering degrees at partners' universities.

Fig. 1. Webpage of Drive MATHS project.

2.2 Project Rules Math

New rules for assessing mathematical competencies form the main idea of the project Rules Math, coordinated by Salamanca University in Spain, with partners at Coimbra Institute of Engineering in Portugal, Dublin Institute of Technology in Ireland, Czech Technical University in Prague, Czech republic, University of Plovdiv Paisii Hilendarski in Bulgaria, Gazi University in Ankara, Turkey, Technical University of Civil Engineering in Bucharest, Romania and Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, see webpage [5].

Project team is working on development of a collaborative, comprehensive and accessible competencies-based assessment model for mathematics in engineering context, and aims to elaborate and collect the resources and materials needed to devise competencies-based assessment courses. Results will be disseminated to European HEIs through the partner networks and also all over the Europe.

Project will focus on mathematical competencies and not just on the mathematical contents, which was the case in earlier times in other educational projects. Since mathematics lecturers are much more familiar with the content view (the mathematical structure) it is a major challenge for them to deal with competencies-oriented assessment goals. This project may provide material for supporting them in this respect. Furthermore, the development of a new mathematical approach is being demanded by engineering and science trainers to motivate students, and also for students to be motivated with mathematics learning.

The screenshot shows the 'Objectives' page of the Rules Math project. The navigation bar includes links for HOME, WELCOME, PARTNERS, OBJECTIVES, DISSEMINATION, and ENGLISH (EN). The main content area is titled 'Objectives' and contains the following text:

The main objective of the RULES_MATH project is to develop assessment standards for a competencies-based teaching-learning system for mathematics in engineering education.

The aims of the project can be summarize as follows:

- (1) To develop a collaborative, comprehensive and accessible competencies-based assessment model for mathematics in engineering context.
- (2) To elaborate and collect the resources and materials needed to devise competencies-based assessment courses.
- (3) To disseminate the model to European HEIs through the partner networks and also promote the dissemination all over Europe.

The institutions involved in RULES_MATH project have long experience in innovation and they have adapted their degrees to the Bologna Accord. Concerning the target groups to be addressed:

- (1) The primary target group of the RULES_MATH project is the pool of mathematical university teachers, trainers, lecturers, and researchers from engineering undergraduate degrees, master degrees, or PhD level (including staff from project partners) who are interested in changing their teaching system in the mathematical teaching/learning field. Including who would like to enhance their mathematical competencies using the most advanced e-learning tools, digital assessment, study materials, and courses.

Fig. 2. Webpage of Rules Math project.

2.3 Project Future Math

New scenarios of the educational process need also new instructional materials, and development of innovative teaching resources was one of the aims of project Future Math – Enhancing Learning and Teaching of Engineering Mathematics with Technology. Project coordinator is at the Tampere University of Applied Sciences in Finland, and partners are Politechnical University in Madrid, Spain, Technical University of Civil Engineering in Bucharest, Romania and Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia. Project goal is to respond to the requirements of the modern society and to make mathematics' learning and teaching more digitalized, effective and accessible. Additionally, the aim is to explore and develop the most motivational, learner centred methods, techniques and resources for engineering mathematics learning and teaching with the help of technology. All the learning resources developed in the project are made available for free under the idea of Open Source or Open Educational Resource (OER) at the project Mathematical Learning Platform, and are accessible from the project webpage [6].

In addition to the open mathematics learning platform with materials and resources, project aims to develop innovative pedagogical methods and techniques not only to teach and learn mathematics but also to assess mathematics' learning. The key approaches are i.e. collective thinking, collaboration and shared problem solving skills - the skills that are necessary for success in working life. Furthermore, project resources are designed in various styles, so that these materials could respect individual learning solutions. Therefore, different learning types are taken into account in the project's material production. In this way, it is also possible to decrease the inequality among different kinds of learners.

Overall, the one main objective of this project is to increase the global large-scale awareness about the possibilities which new ubiquitous technology offers for mathematics learning throughout MLP in order to make mathematics learning more motivational, interesting and to increase accessibility and the alternative modern methods for mathematics learning.

The screenshot shows the FutureMath project website. At the top, there are social media icons and language flags. The navigation menu includes: HOME, PROJECT, DISSEMINATION, SOCIAL, INTRANET, MLP, CONTACT, and a hamburger menu icon. The main content area is divided into three columns:

- Project goal:** Future Mathematics strives to meet the needs of modern society and to make mathematics' learning and teaching more digitalized, effective and accessible. Additionally, the aim is to explore and develop the most motivational, learner centered methods, techniques and resources for engineering mathematics learning and teaching with the help of technology. All the learning resources developed in the project will be made available for free under the idea of Open Source or Open Educational Resource (OER). The project is funded by the EU under the ERASMUS+ Program, with reference
- CONFERENCES:** SEFI, EDUCON, INTED, ICERI
- JOURNALS:** International Journal of Engineering Education, IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON EDUCATION, IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies
- PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION:** Webinar of Future Mathematics, Transnational project meetings, Presentations, Promotion events, Outcomes, Multiplier events

Fig. 3. Webpage of Future Math project.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Engineering students lack essential competences in a world of rapidly changing and dynamic working environments. The later require constant creativity, analytical thinking, perfectionism and adherence to tight deadlines. This lack could influence negatively their future careers. Knowledge cannot be perceived any longer as the end of a goal of an engineering study, it has to be felt as an on-going activity of learning-to-think and learning-to-learn. This will promote a new design for an engineer profile, one which encompasses an engineer willing to manage the tools that our lifestyle requires, for all engineering areas.

Researchers in the three quoted projects strive to apply concepts of mathematical competencies into the practise of teaching maths at engineering study programmes,

and introduce new assessment methods suitable for assessing acquired competencies. These changes include also adapted curricula, change in contents and scope of maths courses within technical study programmes in order to be more suitable for the new goals of getting more competencies, practical skills and abilities than theoretical maths knowledge, and for introduction of ICT assisted solutions of engineering tasks comprising mathematical problems.

Mutual dialogue and cooperation between maths educators and colleagues from engineering departments, not excluding practising engineers, is more than invited for finding adequate and acceptable solution of this difficult and demanding task.

There is no engineering without mathematics, and mathematics can flourish only when reasonably applied in technical sciences and engineering practise, for the benefit of both, scientific theory and real technical applications, making our world a better place for living.

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